

ORGANIC PESTICIDES. PART II. PREPARATION OF SOME *N*-SUBSTITUTED FLUOROBENZAMIDES

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Several *N*-substituted fluorobenzamides have been prepared, preliminary to evaluation of their pesticidal activity.

Organic fluorine compounds have recently assumed industrial importance in the general field of pest control. Amongst the large number of compounds tested so far, substituted fluoroacetamides of the type, FCH_2CONHR , have been extensively investigated by Saunders ("Phosphorus and Fluorine", Cambridge University Press) and Bergman (*J. Sci. Food Agr.*, 1957, 8, 400). These workers have reported the use of such compounds as contact insecticides, potential larvicides and rodenticides. The magnitude of toxicity of FCH_2CONHR suggests that all such compounds are hydrolysed in the animal body to fluoroacetic acid, and the effective part of the molecule is the CH_2F -group (Saunders, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 912; *loc. cit.*). These fluoroacetamides, however, also act as convulsant poisons with delayed action, and special precautions must be taken while handling these toxic compounds.

Keeping these observations in view, we have prepared *N*-substituted fluorobenzamides as potential pesticides. A large number of aromatic fluorine compounds, like, 2,4-difluorobenzoic acid and 2,4,5-trifluorobenzoic acid, have been found to be fungicidal by Finger *et al.* (Ill. State Geological Survey, Circular 199, 1955), indicating that the substitution of fluorine in the aromatic nucleus is likely to confer fungicidal activity on the unsubstituted aromatic compounds. We therefore expect that the conversion of fluorobenzoic acids into the corresponding amides will further enhance their toxicity as certain substituted benzamides, like, *N*-substituted *o*-nitrobenzamides, have already been patented as effective seed disinfectants against many fungi (Brien *et al.*, U.S.P. 2,643,965/1953). Besides, these compounds will be safer to handle than the corresponding fluoroacetamides due to the moderating influence of the aromatic nucleus.

In this communication, *N*-substituted fluorobenzamides, derived from *p*-fluorobenzoic acid and *o*-fluorobenzoic acid, have been prepared. The latter have been obtained from ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate and ethyl anthranilate respectively by the Balz-Schiemann reaction. The fluorobenzoic acids have been converted into the corresponding acid chlorides by the action of thionyl chloride, and the *N*-substituted fluorobenzamides were obtained by the action of different amines on the fluorobenzoyl chlorides in anhydrous benzene medium (Shriner, Fuson and Curtin, "The Systematic Identification of Organic Compounds", p. 227).

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl p-fluorobenzoate was prepared by a modification of the original Balz-Schiemann method (Ber., 1927 60, 1186). Ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate (110 g.) was dissolved in a mixture of HCl (conc., 137 c.c.) and water (198 c.c.) and diazotised as usual with a solution of sodium nitrite (50 g.) in a minimum quantity of water. A solution of sodium fluoborate [prepared by mixing acid boric (46 g.) with HCl (conc., 180 c.c.) and then adding sodium fluoride (120 g.) at intervals at 0°] was added to the diazotised solution at 0°; the resultant product was allowed to stand for one hour, filtered and dried, yield 87 g. (69%). Pyrolysis of diazonium fluoborate at 90-93° afforded crude ethyl *p*-fluorobenzoate, which was extracted with ether, and after removal of ether, was distilled as a reddish yellow liquid, b.p. 112-13°/35-40 mm, yield 61 g. (55%); Schieman *et al.* ("Organic Syntheses" Vol. 2, p. 299, 1943) report b.p. 105-106°/25 mm.

p-Fluorobenzoic Acid.—Ethyl *p*-fluorobenzoate (61 g.) was hydrolysed with 28% ethanolic KOH solution under reflux and *p*-fluorobenzoic acid precipitated as a yellowish solid on neutralisation

with HCl (conc.). Recrystallization from dilute K_2CO_3 solution furnished the pure acid, m.p. 184-85°, yield 27 g. (53%). Schiemann *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) report m.p. 184-86°.

Ethyl o-Fluorobenzoate.—Ethyl *o*-aminobenzoate (80 g.) was diazotised and converted into diazonium fluoroborate, as described above. On pyrolysis at 104-107°, the latter gave crude ethyl *o*-fluorobenzoate which was isolated as a yellowish liquid, b.p. 119-21°/55-60 mm, yield 56 g. (51%). Lit. records b.p. 209° (Beil., IX-137).

o-Fluorobenzoic Acid.—Ethyl *o*-fluorobenzoate (56 g.) was hydrolysed and the acid isolated as described above, m.p. 121-22°, yield 25 g. (49%). Lit. m.p., 126.5°.

p-Fluorobenzoyl chloride was prepared by heating a mixture of *p*-fluorobenzoic acid (27 g.) and thionyl chloride (72 g.) for about 3 hours on a water-bath. After removal of excess of thionyl chloride, *p*-fluorobenzoyl chloride was distilled under reduced pressure as a yellowish liquid, b.p. 42-44°/5 mm, yield 26 g. (83.8%). Cohen (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 99, 1063) reports b.p. 191-92°/104 mm.

o-Fluorobenzoyl Chloride.—A mixture of *o*-fluorobenzoic acid (25 g.) and thionyl chloride (67 g.) was refluxed as described above and *o*-fluorobenzoyl chloride isolated as a colorless liquid, b.p. 48-52°/50-60 mm, yield 23 g. (74.2%). Lit. records b.p. 204-206° (Beil., IX-136.)

N-Substituted Fluorobenzamides.—To a solution of the required amine (*M*), in dry benzene, was added dropwise and with frequent shaking, a solution of the appropriate fluorobenzoyl chloride (1 *M*) in dry benzene. The resultant mixture was refluxed for about an hour and the product left overnight. The solution was filtered, the precipitate was washed with warm benzene and this washing mixed with the original filtrate. The benzene solution was then washed with 2% Na_2CO_3 solution, followed by 2% HCl, and finally with water. The benzene was distilled off and the residual amide was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. In certain cases, pyridine was added in traces to improve the yield of the amides. The following amides have been obtained

TABLE I
N-Substituted fluorobenzamides.
(F denotes fluorobenzamide)

No.	Amides.	M.P.	Yield.	Mol. formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Calc.
1.	<i>p</i> -F	*152-53°	51%	C_7H_6ONF	9.97	10.07
2.	<i>N</i> -Ethyl- <i>p</i> -F	70°	59	$C_9H_{10}ONF$	8.14	8.37
3.	<i>N</i> -(Butyl)- <i>p</i> -F	56°	68	$C_{11}H_{16}ONF$	7.02	7.17
4.	<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>p</i> -F	180°	64	$C_{12}H_{10}ONF$	6.49	6.51
5.	<i>N</i> -Benzyl- <i>p</i> -F	129-30°	66	$C_{14}H_{12}ONF$	5.89	6.11
6.	<i>N</i> -(<i>m</i> -Bromophenyl)- <i>p</i> -F	128°	54	$C_{12}H_9ONBrF$	4.49	4.76
7.	<i>N</i> -(<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl)- <i>p</i> -F	166-67°	60	$C_{12}H_9ONBrF$	4.52	4.76
8.	<i>N</i> -(<i>o</i> -Bromophenyl)- <i>p</i> -F	110-11°	72	$C_{12}H_9ONBrF$	4.51	4.76
9.	<i>N</i> -(<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl)- <i>p</i> -F	109-10°	71	$C_{12}H_9ONClF$	5.52	5.61
10.	<i>N</i> -(<i>o</i> -Tolyl)- <i>p</i> -F	112°	50	$C_{12}H_{11}ONF$	6.02	6.11
11.	<i>N</i> -Phenylamino- <i>p</i> -F	96-97°	40	$C_{12}H_{11}ON_2F$	11.61	12.17
12.	<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>o</i> -F	84-85°	67	$C_{12}H_{10}ONF$	6.46	6.51
13.	<i>N</i> -Benzyl- <i>o</i> -F	39-40°	63	$C_{14}H_{12}ONF$	5.91	6.11
14.	<i>N</i> -(<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl)- <i>o</i> -F	76°	61	$C_{12}H_9ONClF$	5.42	5.61
15.	<i>N</i> -(<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl)- <i>o</i> -F	126-27°	52	$C_{12}H_9ONClF$	5.53	5.61
16.	<i>N</i> -(<i>o</i> -Anisyl)- <i>o</i> -F	110°	34	$C_{14}H_{13}O_2NF$	5.52	5.71

* Lit. m.p. 153°.

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